

Molecular Crowding Bi-salt Electrolyte for Aqueous Zinc Hybrid Batteries

Figure S1. Digital picture of the individual components of a representative example of MCE with 1:4 m Zn/Li – 70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O. The electrolytes were prepared in an argon-filled glove box at room temperature or were bubbled with argon outside the glove box (before performing the experiments) in order to prevent oxygen contamination.

Figure S2. Ionic conductivity of the MCEs, 1:1 m Zn/Li – x:(100-x) wt% PEG/H₂O (x = 0, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90) measured at 25 °C.

Table S1. Comparison of ion conductivity of the MCEs developed in this work with the reported similar examples

Entry	Electrolyte	Electrolyte type	Battery type	Ionic conductivity (ms/cm)	Ref.
1	1m Zn(CF ₃ SO ₃) ₂ in 45:55 wt% PEG400 / H ₂ O	MCE	Rocking chair	Not reported	<i>Small. 18 (2022) 2103345 [1]</i>
2	1m Zn(CF ₃ SO ₃) ₂ in 70:30 wt% PEG400 / H ₂ O	MCE	Rocking chair	Not reported	<i>Energy Storage Mater. 45 (2022) 1084–1091 [2]</i>
3	1m Zn(CF ₃ SO ₃) ₂ in 70:30 wt% PEG400 / H ₂ O	MCE	Rocking chair	1.5	<i>Batter. Supercaps. 5 (2022) [3]</i>
4	30m ZnCl ₂ in H ₂ O	WiSE	Not demonstrated	1.8	<i>Chem. Commun., 2018,54, 14097-14099 [4]</i>
5	2m Zn(CF ₃ SO ₃) ₂ + 21m LiTFSI	WiSE	Hybrid-ion	6	<i>Adv. Energy Mater. 2019, 1902473 [5]</i>
6	1m Zn(TFSI) ₂ + 20m LiTFSI+ urea in H ₂ O	Deep eutectic solvent	Hybrid-ion	1.85	<i>Nano Energy 57 (2019) 625–634 [6]</i>
7	1m Zn(TFSI)₂ + 1m LiTFSI in 70:30 wt% PEG400 / H₂O	MCE	Hybrid-ion	2.4	<i>This work</i>
8	1m Zn(TFSI)₂ + 4m LiTFSI in 70:30 wt% PEG400 / H₂O	MCE	Hybrid-ion	2.2	<i>This work</i>

Figure S3. Tafel plot of the 1:1 m Zn/Li – x:(100-x) wt% PEG/H₂O (y = 0, 50, 70, 80) electrolytes.

Figure S4. Selected Raman spectra of 1:1 m Zn/Li – x:(100-x) wt% PEG/H₂O (y = 0, 50, 70, 80) electrolytes.

Figure S5. Vertically offset differential scanning calorimetry thermograms of 1:1 m Zn/Li – 100 wt% H₂O (a), 1:1 m Zn/Li – 70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O (b) and 1:4 m Zn/Li – 70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O (c).

Although detailed thermal analysis of PEG/water/LiTFSI/Zn(TFSI)₂ mixture is not within the scope of this work, the following aspects could be analyzed according to the existing literature on PEG/water binary mixtures.[7–9]

a) 1:1 m Zn/Li – 100 wt% H₂O: DSC heating cycle features two thermal transitions to the endothermic side, i) step like deviation around –100 °C should be ascribed to the glass transition (T_g) and ii) a relatively sharp endothermic peak owing to the melting process at $T_m = -28$ °C of free water. In the cooling cycle, a clear and sharp exothermic peak due to the crystallization of free water in this aqueous solution is apparent.

b) 1:1 m Zn/Li – 70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O: Heating cycle shows three thermal transitions for this arduous solution, i) T_g around -90 °C, ii) an exothermic peak with an onset temperature (T_c) of -57 °C attributed cold crystallization. After the glass transition event, molecular movement was increased and some metastable crystals of the PEG/water mixture in the aqueous salt solution rearranged to form stable crystals causing this cold crystallization event. iii) a little broader melting peak at $T_m = -38$ °C presumably due to the melting of the PEG/water/salt aqueous mixture and/or free water. Further heating above T_c causes the continuous rearrangement of PEG/water/salt aqueous mixture molecules to cease, so that the crystals melt after their formation leading to the melting process. However, in the cooling cycle, no exothermic peaks were detected.

c) 1:4 m Zn/Li – 70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O: In this case, heating cycle demonstrated only one thermal transition, i.e., T_g around -88 °C, and cold crystallization and melting processes were totally absent.

Computational Methodology:

Each system was simulated by a cubic box, with 5 nm box size to achieve the experimental conditions. The compositions of all investigated systems are summarized in Table S2. The molecular dynamics simulations and the subsequent analysis were performed with the GROMACS 2020 package.[10,11]

Table S2. Composition of all studied systems

System	%mass PEG:Water	[Zn(TFSI) ₂] / [LiTFSI]	N° Zn	N° Li	N° TFSI	N° PEG400	N° Water
1	0:100	1m / 1m	45	45	135	0	2500
2	70:30	1m / 1m	12	12	36	70	690
3	70:30	1m / 4m	12	50	74	70	690
4	0:100	0m / 0m	0	0	0	0	2500

The CHARMM36 force field was used for the PEG400, the Zn²⁺ and Li⁺ atoms. This forcefield has been tested in aqueous simulations with PEG400 showing good agreement with experimental values for properties, such as coordination numbers, number of hydrogen bonds and diffusion coefficients.[12–14] For the TFSI⁻ anion, we used a specific ionic liquid force field from reference.[15] For water, a 4-point model, TIP4P was employed.[16] For all simulations, a time step of 1.0 fs was used. We applied the following MD protocol: i) 5 ns of NVT ensemble, followed by ii) 120 ns of NPT ensemble and iii) a production run of 200 ns. The NVT ensemble was done in order to minimize the forces between our atoms in the system employing a modified Berendsen thermostat to maintain the temperature of the system at 298 K.[17] The NPT ensemble was performed in order to let the system reach the equilibrium volume and density in the desired conditions of 1 bar pressure using the Parinello-Rahman thermostat.[18] For the electrostatic interactions, the Particle-Mesh-Ewald method[19] with a Fourier spacing of 0.12 nm grid size spacing was used. A cut-off distance of 12 Å was used for the long-range electrostatic interactions. The bonds were constrained with the LINCS algorithm.[20] The pair radial distribution functions (RDF) of the zinc cations with the anions and water molecules were computed, in order to identify their coordination environment. The

coordination numbers (C.N.) are calculated by integration of the RDF using as cut-off the first valley from the corresponding RDF.[21]

Results

By applying MD simulations, we investigate the microscopic structure for the investigated systems. We are mainly interested in the hydrogen-bonding pattern between the water molecules and also the coordination environment of the cations and anions in both solutions. To achieve this, we analyse the pair radial distribution functions (RDF) of the water with the zinc and lithium cations, and the TFSI anions in all solutions. The results for the RDF integration are summarized in Table S3.

Table S3. Summary of the coordination numbers (C.N.) of Zn²⁺, Li⁺, and PEG species in the investigated systems. The C.N.s are the RDF integration results from MD simulations of studied systems

System	%mass PEG:Water	[Zn(TFSI) ₂] / [LiTFSI]	^a Total C.N. Zn – H ₂ O	^a Total C.N. Li-H ₂ O	^a Total C.N. TFSI-H ₂ O	^a Total C.N. PEG-H ₂ O
1	0:100	1m / 1m	5.97	3.92	2.53	---
2	70:30	1m / 1m	5.98	3.91	2.24	2.16
3	70:30	1m / 4m	5.95	3.78	2.23	2.18
4	0:100	0m / 0m	---	---	---	---

^aCoordination numbers (C.N.) of water with the Zn²⁺, Li⁺ cations, the TFSI⁻ anions and the PEG (average values, calculated from the RDF).

The coordination numbers for lithium and zinc cations do not change significantly in the presence of PEG400. The cations are always coordinated with water molecules and not with the TFSI anion for all studied systems. The corresponding values agree with previous experimental and computational results.[22–24]

Further analysis is performed by calculating the average number of hydrogen-bonds (ANHB) in all three systems. The following geometric criteria were employed: $135^\circ \leq \angle OHY \leq 180^\circ$ and distance $O-Y < 3.5 \text{ \AA}$ for the acceptor Y of H-bonds between Y and H₂O molecules.

The average values were collected from the snapshots between the first 10 ns till the end of the simulation. The results are presented in Table S4.

Table S4. Summary of the H-bonding analysis from the MD simulations for studied systems

System	%mass PEG:Water	[Zn(TFSI) ₂] / [LiTFSI]	^a ANHB H ₂ O-H ₂ O	^a ANHB TFSI-H ₂ O	^a ANHB PEG400-H ₂ O
1	0:100	1m / 1m	1.66	6.55	0
2	70:30	1m / 1m	1.61	5.91	1.38
3	70:30	1m / 4m	1.22	5.43	1.45
4	0:100	0m / 0m	2.07	0	0

^aANHB = Average number of hydrogen bonds

For the TFSI anion, the average number of hydrogen bonds with water is between 5.4 and 6.6 for systems (1–3). In the case of the PEG400, the values are 1.38 and 1.45 for the systems 2 and 3, respectively. Finally, for the water the corresponding values are reduced from 2.07 for bulk water (system 4) till 1.22 for the 1:4 m Zn/Li–70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O (system 3). This shows how the amount of free water is changing depending on the system composition.

The fraction of “free water” molecules can also be calculated by estimating the total number of water molecules that are coordinated to all Zn²⁺, Li⁺, TFSI⁻ and PEG species and subtracting it from the total number of water molecules in each system.

Figure S6. Radial distribution functions and coordination numbers. In 1:1 m Zn/Li (a-d): Zn with water: in 70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O (a) and 100 wt% H₂O (b); Li with water: in 70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O (c) and 100 wt% H₂O (d). In 1:4 m Zn/Li (e-h): Zn with water: in 70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O (e) and 100 wt% H₂O (f); Li with water: in 70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O (g) and 100 wt% H₂O (h).

Figure S7. Cyclic voltammetry of 1:1 m Zn/Li – 100 wt% H₂O at 1 mV s⁻¹ in three-electrode configuration with Pt as working and Zn as reference and counter electrodes.

Table S5. Comparison of aqueous Zn//LFP hybrid batteries reported in the literature.

Entry	Electrolyte	Cathode composition	LFP mass loading (mg/cm ²)	LFP Nominal Capacity (mAh/cm ²)	Cycles Sp. Capacity Cap. Retention C-rate	Ref.
1	CH ₃ COOLi (15 wt%) + Zn(CH ₃ COO) ₂ (15 wt%)	80:10:10 (LFP:AB:PTFE)	n a	–	125 112 mAh/g 90% 1C	[25]
2	3 M LiCl + and 4 M ZnCl ₂	90:4:6 (LFP:SuperP:PVDF)	0.8–1.1	0.14–0.19	400 120 mAh/g 54% 6C	[26]
3	1M Zn(CF ₃ SO ₄) ₂ + 1M Li(CF ₃ SO ₄)	75:15:10 (LFP:SuperP:PTFE)	1.5	0.25	100 132.2 mAh/g 88.6% 1C	[27]
4	15 m ZnCl ₂ + 1.0 m LiCl	80:10:10 (LFP:SuperP:PVDF)	n a	–	1000 130 mAh/g 76.9% 3C	[28]
5	1 M ZnSO ₄ + 1 M Li ₂ SO ₄	75:15:10 (LFP:AB:PTFE)	1.2	0.2	500 108.4 mAh/g 87.6% 5C	[29]
6	4m Zn(CF ₃ SO ₄) ₂ + 2m LiClO ₄	80:10:10 (LFP:SuperP:PVDF)	4.5	0.76	100 146 mAh/g 66% 0.8 C	[30]
7	1m Zn (TFSI) ₂ + 4m LiTFSI in 70:30 wt% PEG400 / H ₂ O	85:10:5 (LFP:C65:PVDF)	4–5	0.7–0.85	200 120 mAh/g 65% 0.2C	<i>This work</i>

Figure S8. Charge/discharge profiles of Zn/LFP at 0.2C with 1:1 m Zn/Li in 100 wt% H₂O (a), in 50:50 wt% PEG/H₂O (b), in 70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O (c) and 80:20 wt% PEG/H₂O (d).

Figure S9. Coulombic efficiency profiles of Zn//LFP at 0.2C with 1:1 m Zn/Li in 80:20 wt% PEG/H₂O (a), 70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O (b), 50:50 wt% PEG/H₂O (c) and 100 wt% H₂O (d).

Figure S10. Ionic conductivity of the MCEs named 1:y m Zn/Li-70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O (y = 1, 4, 6 and 10) measured at 25°C.

Figure S11. Surface morphology of Zn by FE-SEM before (a) and after (14 days) immersion in electrolytes 1:1 m Zn/Li-100 wt% H₂O (b) and 1:4 m Zn/Li-70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O (c). Scare bar is 10 μm.

Figure S12. Characteristic XRD pattern of zinc before and after immersion (14 days) in electrolytes. Insets show the zoomed region between $2\theta = 10\text{--}20^\circ$

Figure S13. Areal capacity - voltage profiles of Zn//Cu asymmetrical cells in 1:1 m Zn/Li - 100 wt% H₂O (a) and in 1:4 m Zn/Li - 70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O (b), at different areal currents and at a fixed areal capacity of 0.2 mAh cm⁻².

Figure S14. Areal capacity - voltage profiles of Zn//Cu asymmetrical cells in 1:1 m Zn/Li - 100 wt% H₂O (a) and in 1:4 m Zn/Li - 70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O (b), at different areal capacities and at a fixed areal current of 0.25 mA cm⁻².

Figure S15. Long-term Coulombic efficiencies evaluation of Zn//Cu asymmetrical cells in in 1:1 m Zn/Li - 100 wt% H₂O and in 1:4 m Zn/Li - 70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O

Figure S16. Surface morphology of stripped Zn anode at 0.250 mA cm⁻² with the discharge/charge capacity of 0.400 mAh cm⁻² by FE-SEM after 15 cycles in a Zn//Cu cell in 1:1 m Zn/Li - 100 wt% H₂O and in 1:4 m Zn/Li - 70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O (d-f). Scare bar is 100 μm in a, b, d, e and 10 μm in c, f.

Figure S17. Surface morphology of Zn deposition on Cu at 0.250 mA cm^{-2} with the discharge/charge capacity of $0.400 \text{ mAh cm}^{-2}$ by SEM after 15 cycles in a Zn//Cu cell in 1:1 m Zn/Li - 100 wt% H₂O and in 1:4 m Zn/Li - 70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O (d-f). Scare bar is 10 μm

Figure S18. a) Histogram and b) EDS mapping of Zn, C, O and Cu on Cu cathode after 15 cycles at 0.250 mA cm^{-2} with the discharge/charge capacity of $0.400 \text{ mAh cm}^{-2}$ in a Zn//Cu cell in 1:1 m Zn/Li - 100 wt% H₂O.

Cu in 1:4 m Zn/Li – 70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O

Figure S19. a) Histogram and b) EDS mapping of Zn, C, O and Cu on Cu cathode after 15 cycles at 0.250 mA cm^{-2} with the discharge/charge capacity of $0.400 \text{ mAh cm}^{-2}$ in a Zn//Cu cell in 1:4 m Zn/Li - 70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O.

Figure S20. Characteristic XRD pattern of copper (a) and zinc (b) after 15 cycles at 0.250 mA cm^{-2} with the discharge/charge capacity of $0.400 \text{ mAh cm}^{-2}$ in a Zn//Cu cell.

Figure S21. Charge/discharge voltage profiles of Zn//LFP at 0.2C in 70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O with 1:1 m Zn/Li (a) and 1:10 m Zn/Li (b).

Figure S22. Coulombic efficiency profiles of Zn//LFP at 0.2C in 70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O with 1:10 m Zn/Li (a) and 1:4 m Zn/Li (b) and 1:1 m Zn/Li (c).

Figure S23. Charge/discharge voltage profiles of Zn//LFP at different rates from 0.1 to 1C in 1:1 m Zn/Li-100 wt% H₂O (a) and 1:4 m Zn/Li-70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O (b).

Figure S24. Comparative self-discharge of Zn/LFP cells in 1:1 m Zn/Li - 100 wt% H₂O (a, c, e) and in 1:4 m Zn/Li - 70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O (b, d, f) at different resting times. a, b) Voltage–time profiles. c - f) Voltage–normalized capacity profiles. The Profiles i–v (# in c, d; self-discharge profiles) and 1–6 (# in e, f; recoverable capacity after self-discharge) correspond to the respective curves shown in a and b.

Figure S25. Coulombic efficiencies of Zn//LFP cells in 1:1 m Zn/Li - 100 wt% H₂O and in 1:4 m Zn/Li - 70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O for self-discharge (a) and float charge (b) experiments at different resting and floating times, respectively.

Table S6. Comparison of self-discharge of Zn//LFP battery in 1:4 m Zn / Li – 70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O with the state-of-the-art aqueous batteries.

Sl No	Battery type	Cell configuration	Electrolyte	Rest period (h)	Self-discharge (%)	Self-discharge rate (% / h)	Reference
1	ZIB	Zn // Na ₂ V ₆ O ₁₆ .nH ₂ O	0.5 m Zn(ClO ₄) ₂ + 18 m NaClO ₄	360	19.1	0.053	<i>Energy Environ. Sci.</i> , 2021, 14, 4463 [31]
2	Na-ion	NaTi ₂ (PO ₄) ₃ // Na _{0.66} [Mn _{0.66} Ti _{0.34}]O ₂	9.26 m NaCF ₃ SO ₃ + 1 m Na ₂ SO ₄	940	100	0.106	<i>Adv. Energy Mater.</i> 2017, 7, 1701189 [32]
3	Li / K	AC // LMO	40.4 m CH ₃ COOK + 9.8 m CH ₃ COOLi·2H ₂ O	50	52.7	1.054	<i>Energy Storage Materials</i> 20 (2019) 373–379 [33]
4	Zn-polymer	Zn // PANINA/ CC@WBL@ABL	2 M ZnCl ₂ + 3 m NH ₄ Cl	1	7.2	7.2	<i>Adv. Funct. Mater.</i> 2021, 31, 2007942 [34]
5	Proton battery	MoO ₃ // CuFe-TBA	1 M H ₃ PO ₄ in MeCN	6	12.5	2.08	<i>Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.</i> 2020, 59, 22007–22011 [35]
6	ReHAB	Zn // LMO	2M ZnSO ₄ and 1M Li ₂ SO ₄	24	6	0.25	<i>ECS Electrochemistry Letters</i> , 4 (12) A151-A154 (2015) [36]
7	Li-I	Li // Iodine on carbon cloth	1 M LiN(CF ₃ SO ₂) ₂ (LiTFSI) in (DOL)/ (DME) with LiNO ₃ addition	120	7.3	0.061	<i>Nano Lett.</i> 2015, 15, 5982–5987 [37]
8	Zn-Br ₂	Zn // CMK-3	0.2 M TPABr + 0.5 M ZnBr ₂	24	4	0.16	<i>iScience</i> 23, 101348, August 21, 2020 [38]
9	ZIB	Zn // V ₂ O ₅ ·1.6H ₂ O	1 mmol Zn(CF ₃ SO ₃) ₂ in PEG45	24	8.3	0.345	<i>Small</i> 2021, 2103345 [1]
10	aq-LIB	Mo ₆ S ₈ // LiMn ₂ O ₄	20 m LiTFSI	700	25	0.035	<i>Adv. Energy Mater.</i> 2020, 2002440 [39]
11	aq-Zn/Li hybrid	Zn // LFP	1m Zn (TFSI) ₂ + 4m LiTFSI in 70:30 wt% PEG400 / H ₂ O	720	5	0.007	<i>This work</i>

Figure S26. Benchmarking our MCE-based aqueous batteries against other aqueous systems, namely, Pb-acid, Ni-Cd, and Ni-metal hydrides (Ni-MH) batteries as well as against aprotic Li-ion batteries in terms of self-discharge rate. The references (numbers) in the figure correspond to the entries in Table S5.

Figure S27. Comparative float charge of Zn/LFP cells in 1:1 m Zn/Li - 100 wt% H₂O (a, c, e) and in 1:4 m Zn/Li - 70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O (b, d, f) at different float charging times. a, b) Voltage–time profiles. c - f) Voltage–normalized capacity profiles. The Profiles i–v (# in c, d; self-discharge profiles) and 1–6 (# in e, f; recoverable capacity after self-discharge) correspond to the respective curves shown in a and b.

Figure S28. Comparative float charge energies of Zn//LFP cells in 1:1 m Zn/Li - 100 wt% H₂O and 1:4 m Zn/Li - 70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O at different float charging times.

Supporting References.

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